

On ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra

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How to cite this paper: Dr. Areej Tawfeeq Hameed¹, Dr. Ruma Kareem K. Ajeena² and Zainab Radhi Mousa³(2021); On ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra. *Sci Res Jr Eng Comp Sci.* 1(1):-13-22.

Received: May 26, 2021

Revision: May30, 2021

Accepted: June 21, 2021

Published: July 31, 2021

Abstract

The aim of this paper is to introduce and study new algebraic structure, called ARZ-algebra and investigate some of its properties. We give the notion of atom, subalgebra, ideal and ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra and quotient ARZ-Algebras, homomorphism, several theorems, properties are stated and proved.

Keywords

ARZ-algebra, subalgebra, ideal, ARZ-ideal, quotient ARZ-Algebras.

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2010 Mathematics Subject Classification: 06F35, 03G25, 03B52.

INTRODUCTION

W.A. Dudek introduced new of abstract algebras: is called BCC-algebras as a generalization of the concept of set-theoretic difference and propositional calculus and studied some important properties in ([1-6]). In this paper , we introduce new of abstract algebras: is called ARZ-algebras which is a generalization of the concept BCC-algebra and define its subalgebras ideals, atom, star and ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebra .We study quotient of ARZ-algebra and describe its properties. Also, we introduce homomorphism of its.

1. Preliminaries

In this section, certain definitions, known results and examples that will be used in the sequel are described.

Definition 1.1. [3,7]. A **BCC-algebra** is a nonempty set X together with binary internal operation $*$ together with a binary internal operation, for all

$x, y, z \in X$,

$$(i) \quad ((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0,$$

$$(ii) \quad 0 * x = 0,$$

$$(iii) \quad x * 0 = x,$$

$$(iv) \quad x * x = 0,$$

$$(v) \quad x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y.$$

A binary relation (\leq) can be defined by putting $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x * y = 0$.

Proposition 1.2. [3,7]. In the BCC-algebra $(X;*,0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- 1) $z * z = 0$,
- 2) $z * (x * z) = 0$,
- 3) $x = (x * 0) * 0$,
- 4) $((y * z) * z) * y = 0$,
- 5) $0 * x = 0 * y \Rightarrow x = y$.

Proposition 1.3. [3,7]. In BCC-algebra $(X;*,0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- 1) $(x * y) * (z * y) \leq x * z$,
- 2) $x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z$,
- 3) $x \leq y \Rightarrow z * y \leq z * x$,
- 4) $z * x \leq z * y \Rightarrow x \leq y$, (left cancellation law).

Definition 1.4. [4]. A nonempty subset S of a BCC-algebra $(X;*,0)$ is called **subalgebra of X** if $x * y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Definition 1.5. [3]. Let $(X;*,0)$ be a BCC-algebra. I is called an **ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$.

Definition 1.6. [2]. Let $(X;*,0)$ be a BCC-algebra. I is called a **BCC-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

Proposition 1.7. [3,7]. In a BCC-algebra $(X;*,0)$,

- 1- Every BCC-ideal of BCC-algebra is an ideal.
- 2- Every BCC-ideal of BCC-algebra is a subalgebra.

Definition 1.8. [2]. Let $(X;*,0)$ and $(Y;*',0')$ be BCC-algebras. A **homomorphism** is a mapping $f: (X;*,0) \rightarrow (Y;*',0')$ satisfying:

$$f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y), \text{ for all } x, y \in X. \quad \text{Let } I \subseteq X \text{ and } J \subseteq Y.$$

The image of I of X under f is $f(I) = \{f(x) \mid x \in I\}$ and **the inverse image of J of Y** is $f^{-1}(J) = \{x \in X \mid f(x) \in J\}$. The set $\{x \in X \mid f(x) = 0'\}$ is called **the kernel of f** which is denoted by $\ker f$.

Proposition 1.9. [2]. Let $f: (X;*,0) \rightarrow (Y;*',0')$ be a homomorphism of a BCC-algebra X into a BCC-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) $f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) If 0 is the identity in X , then $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .
- (3) $x \leq y \Rightarrow f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Theorem 1.10. [2]. Let $f: (X;*,0) \rightarrow (Y;*',0')$ be a homomorphism of a BCC-algebra X into a BCC-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) If I is a BCC-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a BCC-ideal of Y .
- (2) If J is a BCC-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a BCC-ideal of X .
- (3) $\ker f$ is a BCC-ideal of X .
- (4) $\text{Im}(f)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

2. On ARZ-algebras.

In this section, a algebraic new structure which is called ARZ-algebras is presented . Its subalgebra is defined and several characteristics are given.

Definition 2.1. A BCC-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **ARZ-algebra of X** , if its satisfying the following axioms: for all $x, y \in X$,

(vi) $x * y = 0$ and $y * x \neq 0 \Rightarrow y * x = x$, where $x \neq 0$.

In $(X; *, 0)$ we can define a binary relation \leq is defined by: $x \leq y \Leftrightarrow x * y = 0$.

Example 2.2. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	0	a
b	b	b	0	b	0
c	c	a	c	0	c
d	d	d	b	d	0

It is easy to show that $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Example 2.3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	2	0	1
1	1	0	2	1
2	2	1	0	3
3	3	3	3	0

It is easy to show that $(X; *, 0)$ is not an ARZ-algebra, since $0 * 1 \neq 0$.

Proposition 2.4. In ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the relation defined by (\leq) satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- 1) $x \leq y \Rightarrow x * z \leq y * z$,
- 2) $x \leq y \Rightarrow z * y \leq z * x$,
- 3) $(x * y) * z \leq x * z$,
- 4) $(x * y) * (z * y) \leq x * z$

Proof:

- 1) If $x \leq y$, then $(x * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * y) \Rightarrow (x * z) * (y * z) \leq 0$ & By ii $\Rightarrow (x * z) \leq (y * z)$.
- 2) If $x \leq y$, then $(z * y) * (x * y) \leq (z * x) \Rightarrow (z * y) * 0 \leq (z * x) \Rightarrow (z * y) \leq (z * x)$. ■

Proposition 2.4. In any ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following properties holds: for all $x, y, z \in X$;

- 1) $(x * y) * x = 0$,
- 2) $x * y = 0$ implies that $0 * x = 0 * y$,
- 3) $x * 0 = y * 0$ implies that $x = y$.

Proof.

- 1) Put $z = 0$ in (i), $((x * y) * (0 * y)) * (x * 0) = 0$, implies that $((x * y) * 0) * x = 0$, and by (iii) follows that $(x * y) * x = 0$. ■

Definition 2.5. A nonempty subset S of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **subalgebra of X** if $x * y \in S$, whenever $x, y \in S$.

Proposition 2.6. Let $\{S_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of subalgebras of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proof. Let $x, y \in X$ such that $x \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ and $y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$. This implies that $x \in S_i$ and $y \in S_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$. Since S_i is a subalgebra of X , then $x * y \in S_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$. This implies $x * y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$. Therefore, $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X . ■

Proposition 2.9. Let $\{S_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of subalgebras of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X , where $J_n \subseteq J_{n+1}$, for all $i \in \Lambda$.

Proof. Let $x, y \in X$ such that $x, y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$. This implies that $x \in S_i$ and $y \in S_j$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Furthermore, let $S_j \subseteq S_i$ implies that $x \in S_j$ and $y \in S_j$, for some $i, j \in \Lambda$. Since S_i is a subalgebra of X , it follows that then $x * y \in S_j$, for some $j \in \Lambda$. Therefore, $x * y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$, proving that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$ is a subalgebra of X . ■

3. The ARZ-ideals of ARZ-algebras.

In this section, the ARZ-ideal concept of ARZ-algebra is defined some mathematical facts related to ARZ-ideal are discussed and proved several characteristics.

Definition 3.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra. A subset I of X is called an **ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions:

for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) If $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ then $x \in I$.

Definition 3.2. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra. I is called an **ARZ-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and $(*)$ be a binary operation defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I_1 = \{0, 1, 2\}$, $I_2 = \{0, 3\}$ and $I_3 = \{0, 1, 3\}$ are ARZ-ideals of X .

Proposition 3.4. Every ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra is a subalgebra.

Proof. Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra X , for all $x, y \in X$ and let $x, y \in I$, then $(x * 0) * y \in I$ and $0 \in I$. Hence by (iii), $x * y \in I$ Therefore I is a subalgebra. ■

Proposition 3.5. In an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ every ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra is an ideal.

Proof. If we put $z = 0$ in $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y \in I$, we get $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. ■

Proposition 3.6. If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and J is an ARZ-ideal of I , then J is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof. Since J is an ARZ-ideal of I , then $0 \in J$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ such that

$((x * y) * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that that $((x * y) * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$. By assumption, I is an ARZ-ideal of X , so $x * z \in I$ and $y \in J$. From J is an ARZ-ideal of I , so $x * z \in J$. Therefore, J is an ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Proposition 3.7. Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof. Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of X . It is obvious that $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$. Since $0 \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, it follows that $0 \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$.

Let $(x * y) * z \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ and $y \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. We get that $(x * y) * z \in I_i$ and $y \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, then $x * z \in I_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$, because I_i is an ARZ-ideal of X . So $x * z \in \bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$, proving our theorem. ■

Proposition 3.8. Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ARZ-ideal of X , where $I_i \subseteq I_{i+1}$.

Proof. Let $\{I_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of ARZ-ideals of X . It can be proved easily that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i \subseteq X$. Since I_i is an ARZ-ideal of X for all i , so $0 \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$.

Let $((x * y) * z) \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ and $y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$. It follows that $((x * y) * z) \in I_i$ for some $i \in \Lambda$ and $y \in I_j$ for some $j \in \Lambda$. Furthermore, let $I_i \subseteq I_j$.

Hence $((x * y) * z) \in I_j$ and $y \in I_j$. By assumption, I_j is an ARZ-ideal of X , it follows that $x * z \in I_j$. Therefore, $x * z \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$, proving that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} I_i$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . ■

4. The Quotient of ARZ-Algebra

In this section, we describe congruence on ARZ-algebras and we study quotient of ARZ-algebra and describe its properties.

Definition 4.1. Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra X . Define a **relation** (\sim) on X by: $x \sim y$ if and only if, $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$, as define a relation (\sim) in ([6]).

Theorem 4.2. If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then the relation (\sim) is an equivalence relation on X .

Proof. Let I be an ARZ-ideal of X and $x, y, z \in X$. By (iv), $x * x = 0$ and assumption, $x * x \in I$. That is, $x \sim x$. Hence (\sim) is reflexive. Next, suppose that $x \sim y$. It follows that $x * y \in I$ and $y * x \in I$. Then $y \sim x$, so (\sim) is symmetric.

Finally, let $x \sim y$ and $y \sim z$. Then $x * y, y * x, y * z, z * y \in I$ and $((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0 \in I$ and $z * y \in I$, then $(x * y) * (x * z) \in I$, and since $x * y \in I$, so $x * z \in I$. Similarly, $z * x \in I$. Thus (\sim) is transitive. Therefore (\sim) is an equivalence relation. ■

Proposition 4.3. Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. For any $x, y, u, v \in X$, if $u \sim v$ and $x \sim y$, then $u * x \sim v * y$.

Proof. Assume that $u \sim v$ and $x \sim y$, for any $x, y, u, v \in X$, then $u * v, v * u, x * y, y * x \in I$ and by (i), we see that $((u * x) * (v * x)) * (u * v) = 0$ and $(v * x) * (u * x) * (v * u) = 0$, then by theorem $((u * x) * (u * v)) * (v * x) = 0$ and $(v * x) * (v * u) * (u * x) = 0$. From assumption and I is an ideal of X , these imply that $(u * x) * (v * x) \in I$ and $(v * x) * (u * x) \in I$. This shows that

$$u * x \sim v * x \dots (1).$$

On the other hand, by (i), we have that $((v * x) * (y * x)) * (v * y) = 0$ and

$((v * y) * (x * y)) * (v * x) = 0$. From assumption and I is an ARZ-ideal of X , these imply that $(v * x) * (v * y) \in I$ and $(v * y) * (v * x) \in I$.

Thus $v * x \sim v * y \dots (2)$.

From (1) and (2), $u * x \sim v * y$. This completes the proof. ■

Corollary 4.4. If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then the relation (\sim) is a congruence relation on X .

Proof. By Theorem (4.2) and Proposition (4.3). ■

Definition 4.5. Let I be an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. Given $x \in X$, the **equivalence class** $[x]_I$ of x is defined as the set of all element of X that are equivalent to x , that is, $[x]_I = \{y \in X : x \sim y\}$.

We define the **set** $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$ and a **binary operation** (\circ) on X/I by $[x]_I \circ [y]_I = [x * y]_I$.

Theorem 4.6. If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ with $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$, then the binary operation \circ is a mapping from $X/I \times X/I$ to X/I .

Proof. Let $[x_1]_I, [x_2]_I, [y_1]_I, [y_2]_I \in X/I$ such that $[x_1]_I = [x_2]_I$ and $[y_1]_I = [y_2]_I$. It follows that $x_1 \sim x_2$ and $y_1 \sim y_2$. By Proposition (4.3), $x_1 * y_1 \sim x_2 * y_2$, proving that $[x_1 * y_1]_I = [x_2 * y_2]_I$. ■

Theorem 3.7. If I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$, then $(X/I; \circ, [0]_I)$ is an ARZ-algebra. Moreover, the set X/I is called the **quotient ARZ-algebra**.

Proof. It is clear that $[0]_I \circ [x]_I = [0 * x]_I = [x]_I$ and $[x]_I \circ [0]_I = [x * 0]_I = [x]_I$.

Let $[x]_I, [y]_I, [z]_I \in X/I$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ ([z]_I \circ [y]_I)) \circ ([x]_I \circ [z]_I) &= ([x * y]_I \circ [z * y]_I) \circ [x * z]_I \\ &= [(x * y) * (z * y)]_I \circ [x * z]_I \\ &= [((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z)]_I = [0]_I. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $(X/I; \circ, [0]_I)$ is an ARZ-algebra. ■

Example 4.8. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a set with the following table:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	1	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X ; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebra. It is easy to show that $I = \{0, 1\}$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . We can get that $X/I = \{[0]_I, [1]_I\}$, and

$[1]_I = [2]_I = \{1, 2\}$, . Let \circ be defined on X/I by:

\circ	$[0]_I$	$[1]_I$
$[0]_I$	$[0]_I$	$[0]_I$
$[1]_I$	$[1]_I$	$[0]_I$

Then $(X/I; \circ, [0]_I)$ is an ARZ-algebra.

Proposition 4.9. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be any sets such that $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Suppose that I is an ARZ-ideal of X , then J is an ARZ-ideal of X if and only if J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I .

Proof. Let I be an ARZ-ideal of X with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Suppose firstly that J is an ARZ-ideal of X , then $J/I = \{[x]_I : x \in J\}$, where $[x]_I = \{y \in J : x \sim y\}$, and $X/I = \{[x]_I : x \in X\}$, where $[x]_I = \{y \in X : x \sim y\}$.

Obviously, $J/I \subseteq X/I$ and $[0]_I \in J/I$.

Now, let $([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ [z]_I \in J/I$ and $[y]_I \in J/I$. Then $([x * y] * z)_I = ([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ [z]_I \in J/I$, it follows that $(x * y) * z \in J$ and $y \in J$. By assumption, $(x * z) \in J$. Accordingly, $[x * z]_I = [x]_I \circ [z]_I \in J/I$, this shows that J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I .

On the other hand, suppose that J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I and I is an ARZ-ideal of X with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Thus, $0 \in J$. Let $(x * y) * z \in J$ and $y \in J$. It follows that $([x * y] * z)_I \in J/I$. Since $([x * y] * z)_I = ([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ [z]_I$, so $([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ [z]_I \in J/I$. By hypothesis, $[x * z]_I = [x]_I \circ [z]_I \in J/I$ implies $x * z \in J$. ■

Corollary 4.10. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be any sets such that $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Suppose that I is an ARZ-subalgebra of X . Then J is an ARZ-subalgebra of X if and only if J/I is an ARZ-subalgebra of X/I .

Proof. Similar to that of Proposition (4.9). ■

Corollary 4.11. Let I be ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra X with $I \subseteq J$, then J is an ARZ-ideal of $(X; *, 0)$.

Next, the basic properties of equivalence classes are considered are as the following theorem.

Theorem 4.12. Let I be a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and $a, b \in X$. Then:

- (1) $[a]_I = I \Leftrightarrow a \in I$,
- (2) $[a]_I = [b]_I$ or $[a]_I \cap [b]_I = \emptyset$.

Proof. Let I be a subalgebra of X and $a, b \in X$.

- (1) It is clear due to the fact that $a \sim a$ for all $a \in X$ and $a * a = 0 \in I$, so we get that $a \in [a]_I = I$.

Conversely, let $x \in [a]_I$. Then $x \sim a$, it follows that $x * a, a * x \in I$. By hypothesis, $x \in I$. Hence, $[a]_I \subseteq I$. To show that $I \subseteq [a]_I$, choose $x \in I$. Since I is a subalgebra of X , we have $x * a, a * x \in I$. Thus, $x \sim a$, this means that $x \in [a]_I$ and shows that $I \subseteq [a]_I$. Consequently, $[a]_I = I$.

- (2) Assume that $[a]_I \cap [b]_I \neq \emptyset$. Then there is $x \in [a]_I \cap [b]_I$ such that $x \in [a]_I$ and $x \in [b]_I$. It follows that $x \sim a$ and $x \sim b$, so $a \sim b$ by the symmetric and transitive properties. Thus $[a]_I = [b]_I$. ■

5. Homomorphism of ARZ-algebra

In this section, we introduce the concept homomorphism and we can describe properties of homomorphism of ARZ-algebra, also we give examples and results of it.

Definition 5.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *', 0')$ be ARZ-algebras. A **homomorphism** is a mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ satisfying $f(x * y) = f(x) *' f(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Definition 5.2. In a mapping $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$. The set $\{x \in X | f(x) = 0'\}$ is called **the kernel of f** denoted by $\ker f$.

Definition 5.3. Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a mapping of an ARZ-algebra X into an ARZ-algebra Y , and let $I \subseteq X$ and $A \subseteq Y$. **The image of I of X under f** is $f(I) = \{f(x) | x \in I\}$ and **the inverse image of A of Y** is $f^{-1}(A) = \{x \in X | f(x) \in A\}$.

Next, the basic properties of homomorphism are considered as the following theorem.

Theorem 5.4. Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *', 0')$ be a mapping of an ARZ-algebra X into an ARZ-algebra Y . Then:

- (1) $f(0) = 0'$.
- (2) If 0 is the identity in X , then $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .

(3) f is injective $\Leftrightarrow \ker f = \{0\}$.

(4) $x \leq y$ implies $f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Proof. Assume that $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ is a homomorphism.

(0) Since $0 * 0 = 0$, then $f(0) = f(0 * 0) = f(0) * f(0) = 0'$.

(2) Assume that (0) is the identity in X and $(0')$ is the identity in Y . From (ii), $0' * f(0) = f(0) = 0'$ and $f(0) * 0' = f(0) * (f(0) * f(0)) = f(0) * f(0 * 0) = f(0) * f(0) = 0'$

By (0), we get that $f(0) = 0'$. This show that $f(0)$ is the identity in Y .

(3) Suppose that f is injective and $x \in \ker f$. It follows that $f(x) = 0'$. Since $f(0) = 0'$, so $f(x) = f(0)$. By assumption, $x = 0$. Thus $\ker f = \{0\}$.

Conversely, suppose that $\ker f = \{0\}$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $f(x) = f(y)$. Then we get that $f(x * y) = f(x) * f(y) = 0'$ and $f(y * x) = f(y) * f(x) = 0'$, thus $x * y, y * x \in \ker f$, this means that $x * y = 0 = y * x$. Hence $x = y$, and shows that f is injective.

(4) Let $x \leq y$. It follows that $x * y = 0$. So $f(x) * f(y) = f(x * y) = f(0) = 0'$. Hence $f(x) \leq f(y)$. ■

Theorem 5.5. Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism. Then:

(1) If I is an ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is an ideal of Y .

(2) If I is a subalgebra of X , then $f(I)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

(3) If I is an ARZ-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is an ARZ-ideal of Y .

(4) If J is an ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ideal of X .

(5) If J is a subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a subalgebra of X .

(6) If J is an ARZ-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ is a homomorphism.

(1) Let I be an ideal of X . We see that $0 \in I$, and by theorem (5.4(1)), $0' = f(0) \in f(I)$, so $0' \in f(I)$.

Now, assume that $(f(x) * f(y)) \in f(I)$ and $f(y) \in f(I)$, it follows that $f(x) \in f(I)$, so $x * y, y \in I$. Since I is an ideal of $x, y \in I$ implies that $x \in I$. It follows that $f(x) \in f(I)$. Hence $f(I)$ is an ARZ-ideal of Y .

(2) Let I be a subalgebra of X and $x, y \in f(I)$. Then there exist $a, b \in I$ such that $x = f(a)$ and $y = f(b)$. Since $x * y = f(a) * f(b) = f(a * b) \in f(I)$. Thus $f(I)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

(3) Let I be an ARZ-ideal of X . We see that $0 \in I$, and by theorem (6.4(1)),

$0' = f(0) \in f(I)$, so $0' \in f(I)$.

Now, assume that $(f(x) * f(y)) * f(z) \in f(I)$ and $f(y) \in f(I)$, it follows that $f(x * z) \in f(I)$, so $(x * y) * z, y \in I$. Since I is an ARZ-ideal of $x, y, z \in I$ implies that $x * z \in I$. It follows that $f(x * z) = f(x) * f(z) \in f(I)$. Hence $f(I)$ is an ARZ-ideal of Y .

(4) Let J be an ideal of Y . Then $0' \in J$, we get that $0 = f^{-1}(0') \in f^{-1}(J)$. For any $x, y \in X$, let $(x * y) \in f^{-1}(J)$ and $y \in f^{-1}(J)$. It follows that $(f(x) * f(y)) = f(x * y) \in J$ and $f(y) \in J$. Since J is an ideal of Y , we obtain that $f(x) \in J$. Consequently $x \in f^{-1}(J)$, proving that $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ideal of X .

(5) Let J be a subalgebra of Y and $x, y \in f^{-1}(J)$. Then $f(x) = a$ and $f(y) = b$ for some $a, b \in J$. Thus $f(x * y) = f(x) * f(y) = a * b \in J$, as J is a subalgebra. Hence $x * y \in f^{-1}(J)$.

(6) Let J be an ARZ-ideal of Y . Then $0' \in J$, we get that $0 = f^{-1}(0') \in f^{-1}(J)$. For any $x, y, z \in X$, let $((x * y) * z) \in f^{-1}(J)$ and $y \in f^{-1}(J)$. It follows that

$(f(x) * f(y)) * f(z) = f((x * y) * z) \in J$ and $f(y) \in J$. Since J is an ARZ-ideal of Y , we obtain that $f(x * z) = f(x) * f(z) \in J$. Consequently $x * z \in f^{-1}(J)$, proving that $f^{-1}(J)$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . ■

Theorem 5.6. Let $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism. Then:

(1) $\ker f$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

(2) $\text{Im}(f)$ is a subalgebra of Y .

(3) f is one to one $\Leftrightarrow \ker f = \{0\}$.

Proof. Assume that $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ is a homomorphism.

(1) It is clear that $\ker f \subseteq X$. Since $f(0) = 0'$, so $0 \in \ker f$. It follows that $\ker f \neq \emptyset$.

Let $((x * y) * z) \in \ker f$ and $y \in \ker f$. Then $f((x * y) * z) = 0', f(y) = 0'$.

Since $0' = f((x * y) * z) = f(x * y) * ' f(z) = (f(x) * ' f(y)) * ' f(z)$, but $f(y) = 0'$, then $(f(x) * ' f(z)) = 0'$ imply $f(x * z) = f(x) * ' f(z) = 0'$ i.e., $x * z \in \ker f$.

Therefore $\ker f$ is an ARZ-ideal of X .

(2) Let $a, b \in \text{Im}(f)$, then there exist $x, y \in X$ such that $a = f(x)$ and $b = f(y)$, so $a * ' b = f(x) * ' f(y) = f(x * y) \in \text{Im}(f)$. This proves that $\text{Im}(f)$ is an subalgebra of Y .

(3) Suppose f is one to one, let $x \in \ker f$, thus $f(x) = 0'$, since $f(0) = 0', f(x) = f(0)$ and f is one to one, then $x = 0$. Hence $\ker f = \{0\}$.

Conversely, suppose $\ker f = \{0\}$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $f(x) = f(y)$. Then we get that $f(x * y) = f(x) * ' f(y) = 0'$ and $f(y * x) = f(y) * ' f(x) = 0'$.

Thus $x * y, y * x \in \ker f$, so $x * y = 0 = y * x$ imply Proposition (2.5(3)), $x = y$. Hence f is one to one. ■

Example 5.7. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$. Define an operation $(*)$ on X by :

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1
2	2	2	0

Then, it can be easily show that $(X ; *, 0)$ is an ARZ-algebras. Now, let f be the mapping from X to itself such that $f(0) = 0, f(1) = 0$ and $f(2) = 1$, then we see that $\text{Im}(f) = \{0, 1\}$. So $\text{Im}(f)$ is not an ARZ-ideal of X , since $1 \in \text{Im}(f)$ and $1 * 2 = 1 \in \text{Im}(f)$, but $2 \notin \text{Im}(f)$.

The next proposition holds, whose verification is routine and omitted.

Remark 5.8. Let f be a homomorphism from an ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ to an ARZ-algebra $(Y ; * ', 0')$. Then:

- (1) f is an epimorphism $\Leftrightarrow \text{Im}(f) = Y$.
- (2) f is an isomorphism \Leftrightarrow the inverse mapping f^{-1} is an isomorphism.

Theorem 5.9. Let I be a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$. Defined the map $f: (X ; *, 0) \rightarrow (X/I, \circ, [0]_I)$ by: $f(x) = [x]_I$, for all $x \in X$. Then f is epimorphism, we call f is **the natural homomorphism of X onto X/I** . Furthermore, $\ker f = I$.

Proof. Let I be a subalgebra of ARZ-algebra X and $x, y \in X$. Since

$f(x * y) = [x * y]_I = [x]_I \circ [y]_I = f(x) \circ f(y)$, proving that f is a homomorphism.

Next, we will show f is surjective, let $[x]_I \in X/I$ and $x \in X$. Then $f(x) = [x]_I$, so f is surjective.

Finally, to show that $\ker f = I$, let $x \in \ker f$. We get that $[x]_I = f(x) = [0]_I$, then $x \sim 0$. It follows that $x * 0 \in I$ and $0 * x \in I$. By hypothesis $0 \in I$.

Hence, $x \in I$, this mean $\ker f \subseteq I$. To show that $I \subseteq \ker f$, let $x \in I$. Since I is a subalgebra of X , we have $0 \in I$. Thus $x * 0 \in I$ and $0 * x \in I$.

It follows that $x \sim 0$, so $[x]_I = [0]_I$. Since $f(x) = [x]_I = [0]_I$, then $x \in \ker f$. Accordingly, $\ker f = I$. ■

Theorem 5.10. Let $f: (X ; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y ; \circ, 0')$ be an ARZ-homomorphism, and I be an ARZ-ideal of X contain in $\ker f$. Let g be the natural homomorphism of X onto X/I , then there exists a unique homomorphism h of X/I onto Y such that $f = h \circ g$. Furthermore, h is an injective if and only if $I = \ker f$.

Proof. Define the mapping $h: X/I \rightarrow Y$ by $h([a]_I) = f(a)$ for all $[a]_I \in X/I$. We first show that, h is well-defined.

Let $[a]_I, [b]_I \in X/I$ be such that $[a]_I = [b]_I$. We get that $a \sim b$, so $a * b \in I$ and $b * a \in I$. Since $I \subseteq \ker f$, $a * b \in \ker f$ and $b * a \in \ker f$. Thus $f(a) \circ f(b) = f(a * b) = 0'$ and $f(b) \circ f(a) = f(b * a) = 0'$. From Proposition (2.5(3)), $f(a) = f(b)$. Hence h is well-defined.

We will show that h is a homomorphism. Let $[a]_I, [b]_I \in X/I$. Then $h([a]_I \circ [b]_I) = h([a * b]_I) = f(a * b) = f(a) \circ f(b) = h([a]_I) \circ h([b]_I)$, proving that h is a homomorphism.

Next, to show that $f = h \circ g$. For any $a \in X$, then

$(h \circ g)(a) = (h(g(a))) = h([a]_I) = f(a)$. Hence $h \circ g = f$.

Finally, if $h': X/I \rightarrow Y$ is another function such that $f = h' \circ g$. Let $[a]_I \in X/I$. The equation $h([a]_I) = f(a) = (h' \circ g)(a) = h'(g(a)) = h'([a]_I)$. Thus $h([a]_I) = h'([a]_I)$, for all $[a]_I \in X/I$.

Now, we will show that h is injective if and only if $I = \ker f$. Suppose firstly that h is injective and $a \in \ker f$. Then $h([0]_I) = 0' = f(a) = h([a]_I)$ and since h is an injective, thus $[0]_I = [a]_I$.

It follows that $0 \sim a$, then $0 * a \in I$ and $a * 0 \in I$. By hypothesis, $0 \in I$. Hence, $a \in I$, this mean $\ker f \subseteq I$. This show that $\ker f = I$.

On the other hand, suppose that $\ker f = I$ and $[a]_I, [b]_I \in X/I$ such that $h([a]_I) = h([b]_I)$. Then $f(a) = f(b)$, it follows that $f(a * b) = f(a) \circ f(b) = 0'$. Thus $a * b \in \ker f$. Since $\ker f = I$, so $a * b \in I$.

Similarly, $b * a \in I$. Hence $a \sim b$, proving that $[a]_I = [b]_I$. This show that h is injective. This completes the proof. ■

FUNDAMENTAL THEOREMS

Now, we state the first isomorphism of ARZ-algebras as the following theorem.

Theorem 5.11. (First Isomorphism Theorem)

If f be a homomorphism of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ into an ARZ-algebra $(Y; \circ, 0')$, then the quotient ARZ-algebra $X/\ker(\varphi)$ is isomorphic to $\varphi(X)$.

Proof. Let $\varphi : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; \circ, 0')$ be a homomorphism and let $K = \ker(\varphi) = \{a \in X \mid \varphi(a) = 0'\}$. We get that $X/K = \{[a]_K \mid a \in X\}$, where $[a]_K = \{b \in X \mid a \sim b\}$. From theorem (6.5(5)), we have $\ker(\varphi)$ is an ARZ-ideal of X . Thus $(X/K; *, [0]_K)$ is an ARZ-algebra and $\varphi(X) = \{\varphi(a) \mid a \in X\}$.

Assume that $f : X/K \rightarrow \varphi(X)$ defined by $f([a]_K) = \varphi(a)$, where $[a]_K \in X/K$.

Let $[a]_K, [b]_K \in X/K$ be such that $[a]_K = [b]_K$. Then $a \sim b$, it follows that

$a * b \in K$ and $b * a \in K$. Thus $\varphi(a) \circ \varphi(b) = 0' = \varphi(b) \circ \varphi(a)$, we get that $\varphi(a) = \varphi(b)$. Hence f is well-defined.

Let $[a]_K, [b]_K \in X/K$. We get that

$$\begin{aligned} f([a]_K * [b]_K) &= f([a * b]_K) = \varphi(a * b) \\ &= \varphi(a) \cdot \varphi(b) = f([a]_K) \circ f([b]_K). \end{aligned}$$

This show that f is a homomorphism.

Let $[a]_K, [b]_K \in X/K$ be such that $f([a]_K) = f([b]_K)$. Then $\varphi(a) = \varphi(b)$, it follows that $\varphi(a * b) = \varphi(a) \circ \varphi(b) = 0'$. Thus $a * b \in \ker(\varphi) = K$. Similarly, $b * a \in K$. We see that $a \sim b$, this mean $[a]_K = [b]_K$. Hence f is an injective.

Let $a \in \varphi(X)$. Then there exists $b \in X$ such that $a = \varphi(b)$ and $[b]_K \in X/K$. Thus $f([b]_K) = \varphi(b) = a$. Therefore f is a surjective, proving our theorem. ■

It is easy to check that if I is an ARZ-ideal of ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and J is an ARZ-ideal of I , then J is an ARZ-ideal of X . So, it follows that J is an ARZ-ideal of $I \cup J$ and $I \cap J$ is an ARZ-ideal of I .

Theorem 5.12. (Second Isomorphism Theorem)

If f be an ARZ-homomorphism of an ARZ-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ into an ARZ-algebra $(Y; \circ, 0')$. Let X be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be ARZ-ideals of X . If $I \cup J$ is an ARZ-algebra, then the quotient ARZ-algebras $I/(I \cap J)$ and $(I \cup J)/J$ are isomorphic.

Proof.

Let $\varphi : I \rightarrow (I \cup J)/J$ be a map by $\varphi(x) = [x]_J$ for all $x \in I$. It is obvious that φ is well defined.

Let $[x]_J \in (I \cup J)/J$. If $x \in I$, then $[x]_J = \varphi(x)$. If $x \in J$, then $[x]_J = [0]_J = \varphi(0)$. Thus φ is onto $(I \cup J)/J$.

Consider the equation $\varphi(x * y) = [x * y]_J = [x]_J \circ [y]_J = \varphi(x) \circ \varphi(y)$. Shows that φ is a homomorphism.

Now, let $x \in \ker(\varphi)$. Then we get $\varphi(x) = [0]_J$, so $[x]_J = [0]_J$. It follows that $x \in J$. Since $\ker(\varphi) \subseteq I$, so $x \in I \cap J$. Hence $\ker(\varphi) \subseteq I \cap J$.

On the other hand, let $x \in I \cap J$. Then $x \in J$. Thus $\varphi(x) = [x]_J = [0]_J$, so $x \in \ker(\varphi)$.

Hence $I \cap J \subseteq \ker(\varphi)$. Therefore, $\ker(\varphi) = I \cap J$. From Theorem (6.10), immediately gives us that $I/(I \cap J) \cong (I \cup J)/J$. ■

Next, we state the third isomorphism theorem of ARZ-algebras.

Theorem 5.13. (Third Isomorphism Theorem)

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be an ARZ-algebra and I, J be ARZ-ideals of X , with $I \subseteq J \subseteq X$. Then:

- (1) the quotient J/I is an ARZ-ideal of the quotient X/I , and
- (2) the quotient ARZ-algebra $(X/I)/(J/I)$ is isomorphic to X/J .

Proof.

(1) To show that J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I . It is clear that $J/I \subseteq X/I$ and $[0]_I \in J/I$. Let $(([x]_I \circ [y]_I) \circ [z]_I) \in J/I$ and $[y]_I \in J/I$. Then $((x * y) * z) \in J$ and $y \in J$. Since J is an ARZ-ideal of X , $x * z \in J$, so $([x]_I \circ [z]_I) \in J/I$. Therefore, J/I is an ARZ-ideal of X/I .

(2) Let $\varphi : X/I \rightarrow X/J$ defined by $\varphi([x]_I) = [x]_J$. Assume that $[x]_I = [y]_I$. Then $x \sim y$ determined by I , that is $x * y, y * x \in I$. Since $I \subseteq J$, $x * y, y * x \in J$. Thus $x \sim y$ determined by J , and hence $[x]_J = [y]_J$. Then $\varphi([x]_I) = \varphi([y]_I)$. Therefore, φ is well defined.

Next, to show that φ is onto X/J , let $[x]_J \in X/J$. If $x \in X$ and $x \notin J$, then $[x]_J = \varphi([x]_I)$. If $x \in J$, then $[x]_J = [0]_J = \varphi([0]_I)$. Hence φ is onto. Consider the equation $\varphi([x]_I \circ [y]_I) = \varphi([x * y]_I) = [x * y]_J = [x]_J \circ [y]_J = \varphi([x]_I) \circ \varphi([y]_I)$.

Shows that φ is an ARZ-homomorphism.

Finally, to show that $\ker(\varphi) = J/I$, let $[x]_I \in \ker(\varphi)$. Then $\varphi([x]_I) = [0]_J$, so $[x]_J = [0]_J$. It follows that $x \in J$.

Now, we have $[x]_I \in J/I$. Hence $\ker(\varphi) \subseteq J/I$. Going the other hand, let $[x]_I \in J/I$. We get that $\varphi([x]_I) = [x]_J = [0]_J$, since $x \in J$. Thus $[x]_I \in \ker(\varphi)$, and hence $J/I \subseteq \ker(\varphi)$. Consequently, $\ker(\varphi) = J/I$. By Theorem (6.10), $(X/I)/(J/I)$ is isomorphic to X/J . ■

It turns out that an analogous result of the third isomorphism theorem for groups is also true for ARZ-algebras.

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